

Impact on women's participation in agriculture in India: An assess of new technology

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Abstract

Analysis of women's participation in the Indian agricultural scenario majorly the women involved in agriculture across various Indian states the coordinated management and utilization of various natural resources to satisfy daily family requirements is the responsibility of rural women. It includes land, water, financing technology, and training all of which call for critical examination in the context of India. and also, many literature review notes, the main objection mentioned is to know the women's participation rate in agriculture and understand the new technology in the agriculture sector finally suggestions including that is creating chances for work and end of the article the importance of women in agricultural development and their contributions to food security and other related fields have been gradually more apparent over time. Over 80% of rural women in India work in agriculture. A paradigm change toward economic growth may be achieved through empowering and mainstreaming the workforce of rural women in agriculture. It will improve food and nutrition security and reduce poverty and hunger.

Keywords: New technology, agriculture sector, empowering, food security, new technology, etc.

Introduction

In agricultural development and related industries, women play a big and important role. Regional differences are significant in the kind and degree of women's engagement in agriculture. Yet, women actively participate in a variety of agricultural occupations despite these variations. According to the 2011 Census, of all female major workers, 55% were agricultural laborers and 24 percent were cultivators. The gender gap in land ownership in agriculture is reflected in the fact that women only controlled 12.8 percent of the operating holdings. Also, women possess concentrated operational holdings (25.7 percent) in the marginal and small holdings groups. Compared to urban women, rural women have a much greater percentage of involvement in labor (41. Percent).

According to the Economic Survey 2017–18, as more males move from rural to urban areas, the agricultural sector is becoming more "feminized," with more women taking on different occupations such as farmers, business owners, and laborers There is factual proof that women play a critical role in maintaining regional agro-biodiversity and

guaranteeing global food security. The coordinated management and utilization of various natural resources to satisfy daily family requirements is the responsibility of rural women. This calls for improved access for women farmers to resources including land, water, financing, technology, and training, all of which call for critical examination in the context of India. In addition, increasing agriculture output will depend on women farmers' rights. Women's varying access to resources including land, finance, water, and seeds. Gender-specific interventions must be used in agriculture to boost productivity since women predominate at all stages of the agricultural value chain-production, pre-harvest, post-harvest processing, packaging, and marketing. An "inclusive transformational agricultural strategy" should focus on gender-specific interventions to boost the productivity of small farm holdings, include women as active actors in rural change, and involve both men and women in extension services with gender competence. Many factors contribute to the poor performance of agriculture in many developing nations. Women don't have access to the tools and chances they need

to use their time most effectively, which is one of these barriers. Women work as workers, entrepreneurs, and farmers, yet almost everywhere they encounter more severe barriers to accessing markets, services, and productive resources than males do. These women collectively are regarded as members of the female agricultural labor force and the barriers they encounter. Managing complex households and pursuing different forms of subsistence are often tasks that rural women handle.

Maintaining and enhancing agricultural productivity requires access to new technology. There are gender disparities in a variety of agricultural technology, including equipment and machinery, better plant and animal breeds, fertilizers, and management and pest control methods. Gender disparities in access to and adoption of new technologies, as well as in the usage of purchased inputs and existing technologies, are caused by a number of limitations, such as the gender gaps mentioned above.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on secondary data gathered from Indian and Karnataka annual reports, journals, websites, theses, and Percentage distribution of workers in usual status (ps+ss) by broad industry division during PLFS (2017-18), PLSF 2016-17) PLFS (2018-19), PLFS (2019-20) and PLFS (2020-21) publications, Agriculture statistics at a glance 2021, Various.

Review of Literature

Women and Agricultural Productivity: Reframing the Issues this article will make the case that a large portion of the scholarly literature on women's agricultural production has taken turns that are not conducive to illuminating the key policy issues. Similarly, to this, the policy discussion has frequently focused on incorrect problems. The essential question, which is, to put it simply, where the returns to development expenditures are highest, receives little attention in the literature. It also doesn't offer any insight into the more specific issues of how to boost agricultural output and guarantee that women may profit from these improvements.

Catherine Ragasa (2012) ^[9]. **Gender and Institutional Dimensions of Agricultural Technology Adoption: A Review of Literature and Synthesis of 35 Case Studies** Through analysis of current data on gender variations in access to and adoption of new technologies that affect labor and agricultural production as well as access to employment and economic opportunities is provided in this study. In order to ensure that their requirements are met, how can we increase farmers' adoption of new technologies? And what role do they play in determining the research agenda and innovation processes? These are the two particular research topics that this article addresses.

Suramya Joshi and Vashima Veerkumar (2013) ^[7]. **Research and Development in Indian Agricultural Technology: with Special Reference to Women** The purpose of this study is to use secondary data sources to analyze the participation of women in agriculture across different Indian states. An attempt was made to carefully gather the information and analyze the trend of women's participation in each state. With only a few notable exceptions, including Kerala, Punjab, and West Bengal, where women are actively

involved in non-agricultural activities like the household industry, the service sector, etc., the study amply demonstrates the active involvement and participation of women in the agricultural sector in nearly all of the states.

Dr Mun Mun Ghosh and Dr Arindam Ghosh (2014) ^[2] **Analysis of Women's Participation in Indian Agriculture** this study analyzed that the goal of this study is to analyze the involvement of women in agriculture across various Indian states using secondary data sources. An effort was made to thoroughly compile the data and analyze the trend of women's involvement in each state. With a few notable exceptions, such as Kerala, Punjab, and West Bengal, where women are actively engaged in non-agricultural activities like the household industry, and service sector. the study clearly demonstrates the active involvement and participation of women in the agricultural sector in almost all of the states.

Muzna Alvi. Prapti Barooah, Shweta Gupta, Smriti Saini (2014) ^[5] **Women's access to agriculture extension amidst COVID-19: Insights from Gujarat, India and Dang, Nepal** in this study COVID-19-induced lockdowns have had far-reaching impacts on the rural sector, particularly on women farmers.

These impacts have been exacerbated by a lack of access to reliable and timely agriculture information. Using panel phone survey data from India and Nepal, we study how women's access to agricultural extension was impacted by the lockdowns and its effect on agricultural productivity. We find that women's already low access to formal extension was reduced further, leading to an increased reliance on informal social networks. In both countries, nearly 50% of farmers reported negative impacts on productivity due to the inaccessibility of information during the lockdown.

Objectives

1. To assess the women's participation rate in the Agricultural sector in India.
2. To study the new technology in the agriculture sector.

Women's participation in agricultural activities

Throughout every region of developing countries, women contribute significantly to agriculture and rural economic activities. In many places of the world where economic and social forces are affecting the agriculture sector, their functions vary significantly between and within regions and are changing quickly. Modern supply networks for high-value agricultural products and the advent of contract farming, for instance, present different opportunities and challenges for women than for men. These distinctions result from the limitations placed on women as well as their various roles and duties. Rural women frequently oversee complicated households and employ several means of subsistence

Women engage in agriculture in a variety of roles, including as independent farmers, unpaid farmworkers on family farms, and paid or unpaid labourer on other farms and agricultural enterprises. At both the subsistence and commercial levels, they are engaged in agriculture and cattle production. They run diverse agricultural operations with a focus on producing fish, raising cattle, and growing food and income crops. "The multitasking potentiality of female

labour bought significant propositions for agricultural productivity, rural production, economic vitality, household food security, family health, family economic security, and welfare.” “Multi-dimensional role of women: – Agricultural activities: Sowing, transplanting, weeding, irrigation,

fertilizer application, plant protection, harvesting, winnowing, storing, etc. – Domestic activities: Cooking, child rearing, water collection, fuel wood gathering, household maintenance, etc. – Allied activities: Cattle management, fodder collection, milking, etc.” (Deora,)

Table 1: Share of agricultural women labourers worldwide

Economically Active Population									
	Total (Thousands)			Female share (% of total)			Agricultural share of Economically Active women (%)		
	1980	1995	2010	1980	1995	2010	1980	1995	2010
World	1894978	2755394	3282308	38.1	39.6	40.5	53.5	48.7	42.0
India	259177	364665	491326	26.8	28.2	28.6	82.6	71.5	61.8

Source: FAO (2011). Women in agriculture

In the above table, the calculation of economically active participation in the world has been done from 1980 to 2010. This table shows the share of women workers in the world and in India. The total labor participation in the world in 1980 was 1894978 thousand, in 1995 it was 2755394 thousand in 2010 it increased to 3282308 thousand and in India, it was 259177 thousand in 1980 and 3649565 thousand in 1995. continued like this and increased to 491326 in 2010. Similarly, the participation of women in the world was 38.1% in 1980 and increased by 40.5% in 2010. Similarly, in India, it was 26.8% in 1980 and increased to 28.6% in 2010. Similarly, the share of economically active people in agriculture worldwide was 53.5% in 1980 but decreased by 42.0% in 2010, and in India, it was 82.6% in 2010. This means that the participation rate of women in the agricultural sector is decreasing.

42 percent of all agricultural workers worldwide are women, yet they still experience considerable discrimination in terms of having access to credit and other financial services,

equitable pay, ownership of land and livestock, and involvement in decision-making bodies. The FAO combats this discrimination on two levels: at the governmental level, FAO works to ensure that laws support, gender equality; at the individual level, FAO equips women with entrepreneurial and business planning skills to increase their independence and capacity to participate in the local economy (Food and Agricultural Organization 2020).

“Rural women often manage complex households and pursue multiple livelihood strategies. Their activities typically include producing agricultural crops, tending animals, processing and preparing food, working for wages in agricultural or other rural enterprises, collecting fuel and water, engaging in trade and marketing, caring for family members, and maintaining their homes. Many of these activities are not defined as “economically active employment” in national accounts but they are essential to the wellbeing of rural households” (Team and Doss, p. 2).

Table 2: Percentage-wise distribution of workers in the Division of Agricultural labors usual status

years	Rural			Urban			Rural + Urban		
	Male	Female	persons	Male	female	persons	male	female	persons
2020-21	53.8	75.4	60.8	5.3	10.4	6.5	39.8	62.2	46.5
2019-20	55.4	75.7	61.5	5.0	8.2	5.7	40.0	59.9	45.6
2018-19	53.2	71.1	57.8	4.9	7.8	5.5	38.3	55.3	42.5
2017-18	55.0	73.2	59.4	5.4	9.1	6.1	40.2	57.0	44.1

Source: Percentage distribution of workers in usual status (broad industry division during PLFS (2017-18), PLFS (2018-19), PLFS (2019-20), and PLFS (2020-21)

In the above table, we observe the rate of change in female and male labor participation rate from 2017-18 to 2020-21 divided into three categories namely rural, urban, and combined rural and urban. The proportion of Female Labor and Proportion of Male Labor and Total Continued We have measured the proportion of female labor and the proportion of male labor and total in both rural and urban areas as a percentage Maintaining and enhancing agricultural

productivity requires access to new technology. There are gender disparities in a variety of agricultural technology, including equipment and machinery, better plant and animal breeds, fertilizers, and management and pest control methods. Gender disparities in access to and adoption of new technologies, as well as in the usage of purchased inputs and existing technologies, are caused by a number of limitations, such as the gender gaps mentioned above.

Table 3: State-wise Classification of Agricultural Workers – 2011

States	Male Agricultural Labour (Main and Marginal)	Female Agricultural Labour (Main and Marginal)
Jammu & Kashmir	414344	133361
Himachal Pradesh	103060	71918
Punjab	1239445	349010
Chandigarh	1375	312
Uttarakhand	286540	116761
Haryana	1041241	486892
Delhi	31352	8123
Rajasthan	2132669	2806995

Uttar Pradesh	13803442	6135781
Bihar	12570717	5774932
Sikkim	12883	13103
Arunachal Pradesh	18377	17794
Nagaland	31857	31105
Manipur	46032	68886
Mizoram	22488	19299
Tripura	214106	139512
Meghalaya	106342	92022
Assam	1129210	716136
West Bengal	7452814	2736028
Jharkhand	2341700	2094352
Odisha	3481836	3258157
Chhattisgarh	2344549	2747333
Madhya Pradesh	6310657	5881510
Gujarat	3611622	3189824
Daman & Diu	362	410
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	5453	12346
Maharashtra	6774538	6711602
Andhra Pradesh	8130022	8837732
Karnataka	3283279	3872684
Goa	14816	11944
Lakshadweep	0	0
Kerala	857995	464855
Tamil Nadu	4842707	4763840
Puducherry	42794	25597
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	3744	1037

Source: Agriculture statistics at a glance 2021

In the above table, we note the state-wise participation rate in agriculture among male and female laborers as per the Agricultural Statistics an Insight 2011 report. "We conclude that accurate, current, regionally specific information and analysis is necessary for good gender-aware agricultural policymaking. Data collection has improved substantially over the last decades, as has our understanding of the complexity of women's roles and the need to collect data not only on primary activities but on all women's activities. Data are needed to better understand gender roles in agriculture and how they change over time and in response to new opportunities." (Team and Doss, p. 35)

"The contribution of women to agricultural and food production is clearly significant. However, it is impossible to verify empirically the share produced by women because agriculture is usually a venture among household members and involves a range of resources and inputs that cannot be readily assigned by gender." (Team and Doss, p. 35) Maintaining and enhancing agricultural productivity

requires access to new technology. There are gender disparities in a variety of agricultural technology, including equipment and machinery, better plant and animal breeds, fertilizers, and management and pest control methods. Gender disparities in access to and adoption of new technologies, as well as in the usage of purchased inputs and existing technologies, are caused by a number of limitations, such as the gender gaps mentioned above.

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Table 4: Production and Use of Agricultural Inputs in India

Program	unit	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
1. Seeds											
1) Production of breeder seeds	Thousand Qtls.	123.38	110.20	82.29	86.21	90.37	110.71	105.08	104.26	92.7	91.16
2) Production of Foundation seeds	Lakh Qtls.	22.26	16.17	17.43	15.76	14.95	22.09	19.54	18.00	22.25	24.12
3) Distribute on of certified/quality seeds	Lakh Qtls.	294.85	313.44	301.39	303.12	304.09	348.58	352.01	320.41	383.72	421.09
2. Consumption of chemical fertilizers											
Nitrogenous (N)	thousands	17300	16821	16750	16946	17372	16735	16958	17628	19100	20404
Phosphatic (P)	thousands	7914	6653	5633	6098	6979	6705	6854	6968	7662	8978
Potassic (K)	thousands	2576	2062	2099	2532	2402	2508	2779	2779	2607	3154
Total (N+P+K)	thousands	27790	25536	24482	25576	26753	25949	26591	27375	29369	32536
Per hectare	kgs	142.05	131.46	121.83	128.94	135.76	123.41	127.55	132.57	133.44	137.15
3. Consumption											
Pesticides (technical grade material)	Thousands of tones	52.98	45.62	60.28	56.27	56.72	58.63	63.41	59.67	61.70	53.2

Source: Agricultural statistics at a Glance-2021

In this table sources collected from Agricultural Statistics at a Glance 2021 in this table, we know about the technological change in agriculture from 2011-12 to 2020-2021. What was the quantity of HYV seeds in 2011-12 similar in 2020-21 H.Y.V. In this table, we can know the number of seeds in detail, how much chemical fertilizers were used initially in 2011-12 and now in 2020-21 how much use has increased, and how much change in total production has occurred due to that increase.

Women and men and farmers must have equal access to extension services and training opportunities. Additionally, extension delivery methods must provide equal opportunity for demand articulation and access to extension services between women and men. Finally, training and recruiting women extension agents is necessary to implement a gender-responsive extension system.

“The gender issues in the research organizations pertain to both gender balanced staffing and application of gender-sensitive approaches to respond to the needs and problems of both women and men farmers.” (Ragasa, p. 21) To improve the amount of food produced per hectare of land, farmers utilize chemical fertilizers. H.Y.V. seeds are used, which causes the natural fertility of the population to decline over time. Increasing the amount of chemical energy used is necessary. Fertilizers. Farmers in the village of Qila ka Nangla, close to the Aligarh district, are applying chemical fertilizers three times in a single season, according to a survey. The public is informed on the usage of chemical fertilizers.

The purpose of agricultural technology is to facilitate and improve field labour. Several new agricultural advancements are made every year, along with a few ground-breaking technologies. Agriculture consultants, food producers, and technology managers must be cognizant of the most recent technological advancements as agribusiness develops and modernizes.

Over 58% of India's population relies primarily on agriculture as a source of income, making India one of the biggest participants in this industry globally. India is the greatest producer of milk, pulses, and spices in the world, as well as the country with the biggest herd of cattle (buffaloes), wheat, rice, and cotton plantings. It ranks second in the world for the production of wheat, rice, cotton, sugar, farmed fish, fruit, vegetables, tea, and other agricultural products. Around half of the population of the nation is employed in the agriculture industry, India has the distinction of having the second-largest agricultural land area in the world. In order to provide us with food, farmers, therefore, become a crucial component of the business.

“Many past technologies have failed because they were not able to engage farmers and other end-users into the whole innovation process starting from the upstream planning and priority-setting. Activities can be initiated to promote greater linkages among researchers, extension agents, farmers, and other innovation actors. Poor women and men farmers and their organizations need to be funded for their participation and active engagement in key priority-setting and innovation platforms. Other innovative ways to link research, service providers, and farmers should be promoted, such as hosting women's organizations at the research institute or community information and resource centers with regular interactions with researchers and

women and men farmers.” (Ragasa, p. 42)

Suggestions

1. Boosting earnings. In India, the pace of agricultural change is quite sluggish.
2. Creating chances for work.
3. Taking steps to lower agricultural hazards.
4. Building up the agricultural infrastructure.
5. Strengthening rural life's standard of living.

Conclusion

The core of the agricultural workforce and an essential component of the Indian economy are women. The importance of women in agricultural development and their contributions to food security, agriculture, and other related fields have more apparent over time. The modern agriculture industry is simultaneously changing in a number of different areas. Yet its main objective is to use agricultural technology to increase crop yields through improved management and planning. Modern agricultural technology supports more productive and sustainable farming practices, which benefits farmers in the agribusiness sector.

References

1. Aryal JP, Farnworth CR, Khurana R, Ray S, Sapkota TB, Rahut DB. Does women's participation in agricultural technology adoption decisions affect the adoption of climate-smart agriculture? Insights from Indo-Gangetic Plains of India. *Review of Development Economics*. 2020;24(3):2343-2360. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/rode.12670>
2. Ghosh M, Ghosh A. Analysis of women participation in Indian agriculture. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 2014;19(5):1-6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-19540106>
3. Doss CR. Designing agricultural technology for African women farmers: lessons from 25 years of experience. *World Development*. 2001;29(12):2075-2092. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(01\)00088-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(01)00088-2)
4. Doss CR. Women and agricultural productivity: reframing the issues. *Development Policy Review*. 2018;36(1):35-50. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/dpr.12243>
5. Duvvury N. Women in agriculture: a review of the Indian literature. *Economic and Political Weekly*. 1989;24(43):WS112.
6. Gebre GG, Isoda H, Rahut DB, Amekawa Y, Nomura H. Gender differences in the adoption of agricultural technology: the case of improved maize varieties in southern Ethiopia. *Women's Studies International Forum*. 2019;74:102264. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2019.102264>
7. Joshi S, Veerkumar V. Research and development in Indian agricultural technology: with special reference to women. In *Research Journal. Family, Community and Consumer Science, International Science Congress Association*. 2013;1(9):7-16.
8. Mohammad AA, Shweta S. Agriculture information needs of farm women: a study in State of North India. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*.

- 2014;9(19):1454–60. Available from:
<https://doi.org/10.5897/AJAR2014.8503>
9. Ragasa C. Gender and institutional dimensions of agricultural technology adoption: a review of literature and synthesis of 35 case studies. [n.d.]; c2012. p. 1-57.
 10. Rola-Rubzen MF, Paris T, Hawkins J, Sapkota B. Improving gender participation in agricultural technology adoption in Asia: from rhetoric to practical action. *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*. 2020;42(1):113-125. Available from:
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aep.13011>
 11. Sadaf S, Javed A, Luqman M. Preferences of rural women for agricultural information sources: a case study of district Faisalabad, Pakistan. 2006;2(3).
 12. FAO, editor. *Women in agriculture: closing the gender gap for development*. FAO; c2011.

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